

Science

PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY MEASUREMENT OF SUGAR INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH: AN APPLICATION OF DEA

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Abstract

There are fifteen sugar mills in Bangladesh under Bangladesh Sugar and Food Industries Corporation (BSFIC). But most of all the mills are being run with losses. For this reason the researchers have taken an initiative to measure the relative efficiencies of individual small size sugar mills as well as large size sugar mills in Bangladesh and to set a target of minimum utilization of inputs in order to maximize production level compared to relatively efficient sugar mills. Besides, an attempt has been taken to provide suggestions to improve efficiencies of the inefficient sugar mills. The study is based on the average data of 2004 to 2013 of six sugar mills. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is applied for assessing efficiencies of individual selected sugar mills. Only input-oriented DEA and output-oriented DEA with CRS technology are used as the main tools to estimate the efficiency measurement in this paper. The objective of the study is to introduce the technique and demonstrate it through an example to show how relative efficiencies can be determined and identify units that are relatively less efficient. On an average, the technical efficiency of sugar mills in the sample has been found approximately 0.97 percent.

Keywords: Productive Efficiency; Technical Efficiency; DEA.

JEL Code: G20; G21; N20.

Cite This Article: Professor Dr. Md. Abu Sina, and Dr. Md. Abdus Sabur. (2017). "PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY MEASUREMENT OF SUGAR INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH: AN APPLICATION OF DEA." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 5(7), 354-362. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.837536>.

1. Introduction

Sugar industry in Bangladesh is the second largest agro-based processing industry which has a lion's share in accelerating industrialization process and bringing socio-economic changes in under developed rural areas. According to the recommendation of FAO and Bangladesh Nutritious Council, about 9.00 kilograms of sugar is required per head annually for Bangladeshi citizens. For 16 crore people of Bangladesh, the total demand of sugar per year is estimated

about 15.00 lakh metric tons of sugar. But the production capacity of 15 sugar mills is only 2.10 lakh MT of sugar. It is clear that the production capacity of sugar of 15 sugar Mills and imported sugar from foreign countries have been fulfilling the demand of sugar of our country. About 15,000 employees are engaged in the sugar mills and near about 2 lac acres of land are used in sugarcane cultivation (BSFIC, 2010). The sugar mills in Bangladesh have severe problems of operational management and suffering from losses. To reduce the losses of the sugar mills, to save the hard earning foreign currency, to help the sugarcane cultivators and to survive the sugar mills to the near future, efficient and effective management is highly essential for the sugar industry. This paper is an initiative to review the using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). The researchers have emphasized on the meaning of various concepts of DEA with an empirical analysis.

2. Objective of the Study

The main objective of this paper is to measure operating efficiency of the selected sugar mills of Bangladesh. To attain the main objective some specific objectives are assigned as follows:

- i. To know about the position of the sugar mills under study;
- ii. To measure the operating efficiency as well as underutilization position of the selected sugar mills in Bangladesh.
- iii. To recommend suggestions for enhancing the management performance as well as efficiencies of the sugar mills in Bangladesh.

3. Research Methodology

The analysis of efficiency is done based on secondary data and theory of production. A production function gives the maximum possible output that can be produced from given combination of inputs with a given level of technology. Production is said to be efficient if there is no way to produce more output with the same inputs or to produce the same output with less inputs.

Population of the study regarding sugar mills is 15. Six sugar mills (40%) are selected as sample from fifteen sugar mills under Bangladesh Sugar and Food Industries Corporation (BSFIC) for input-output measurement. Three sugar mills from large size (daily crushing capacity 15,000 (Metric Tons) and three from small size (daily crushing capacity 1,016(Metric Tons) were selected for the purpose of input-output measurement. All the selected sugar mills are running under direct control of Bangladesh Government. The sample was selected purposively keeping in mind the different areas of Bangladesh. Moreover the sample units are selected following the rules of stratified sampling technique. The list of the selected sample sugar mills are as follows:

Table 1: Sample Sugar Mills

SL #	Short Name	Full Name	Year of Establishment	New District	DCC*
1.	TSM	Thakurgaon Sugar Mills Ltd.	1959	Thakurgaon	1,500
2.	NBSM	North Bengal Sugar Mills Ltd.	1933	Natore	1,500
3.	KSM	Kushtia Sugar Mills Ltd.	1966	Kushtia	1,500
4.	SHSM	Shyampur Sugar Mills Ltd.	1967	Shyampur	1,016

5.	C & Co	Carew & Co. (Bangladesh) Ltd.	1938	Chuadanga	1,016
6.	FSM	Faridpur Sugar Mills Ltd.	1977	Faridpure	1,016

Source: Annual reports of BSFIC. *DCC = Daily Crashing Capacity.

The study has been conducted covering the period of 10 (ten) years from 2004 to 2013. This period is considered on the basis of availability of data, reasonable study to construct the best decision and provide suitable comments over the period. The study is conducted through secondary data collected from the offices of the mills under study. DEA is used for measuring efficiency of the mills.

4. Review of Related Literature

Ramaswamy (1990) estimates partial productivity of labor and of capital, and relative efficiency using unit level data for four industries. He uses relative efficiency index. His analysis indicates that capital intensity and partial productivity are sensitive to alternative measure of firm size. Partial factor productivity of labor and of capital also does not exhibit any significant relationship with firm size when size is measured in terms of employment. However, a positive relationship is observed between capital-labor ratio and investment size of the unit. Labor productivity rise while capital productivity falls as the investment size of the unit increases. His analysis suggests existence of increasing returns to scale and thus rejects the assumption of constant return to scale.

Salim, R. A. (2006) wrote an article titled, “Measuring Productivity Efficiency Incorporating Firms’ Heterogeneity: An Empirical Analysis.” He stated that productive performance of firms in the same industry vary even if they use the identical set of inputs and production technology. He found that average rates of productive efficiency ranges from 60 to 81 percent in different sub-sectors of the Bangladesh food manufacturing industries. Firms are producing far away from their potential frontier. There is still scope to increase productive efficiency from the given level of inputs and technology in Bangladesh.

Farnandez & Nuthall (2009) made a study on “Technical Efficiency in the Production of Sugarcane in Central Negros Area, Philippines: An Application of Data Envelopment Analysis”. They found that the sources of inputs used inefficiency in sugarcane production in Central Negros Area, Philippines. Non-parametric Data Envelopment Analysis was used to determine the relative technical, scale and overall technical efficiencies of individual farms which used the same types of inputs and produce the same output (cane).

Bangladesh Enterprise Institute (2010) prepared a report entitled, “Productivity Analysis of Selected SMEs in Bangladesh.” Three measures of productivity like labor productivity, capital productivity and total factor productivity were used in the report. Four sub sectors such as plastics, agro-tools, pond fisheries and vegetable were considered and the results of technical efficiency, pure technical efficiency and scale efficiency were calculated by using DEA. The study found that there was small difference in the productivity performance between base line and benchmark firms although applying same production technology for the same product.

H. Saranga and B. V. Phani (2012) jointly wrote an article entitled, “The Indian Pharmaceutical Industry – An Overview on Cost Efficiency using DEA.” They used both

constant return to scale (CCR) and variable return to scale (BCC) models in order to find scale efficiency and pure technical efficiencies of the 44 companies. The results of DEA have been analyzed along with their compounded annual growth rate to see if internal efficiencies and growth rate are related in the Indian Pharmaceutical Industry. They also used regression analysis to see the correlation between various inputs/ outputs and growth rates.

These reviews show that no initiative is conducted to measure efficiency of the sugar mills in Bangladesh following DEA. So, the researchers have chosen the topic.

5. Concepts of DEA

The term Data Envelopment Analysis was first introduced by Charnes, Cooper and Rhodes (1978) who proposed an input oriented model with constant returns to scale. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is an increasingly popular management tool. DEA offers several characteristics that are quite unique and useful in comparison with traditional financial analysis methods like ratio analysis or regression analysis. Although all these techniques have their own advantages and disadvantages. One of the most important features of DEA is the ability to compare many parameters simultaneously and come up with a scalar measure of overall performance (Saranga & Phani, 2012). DEA is a non-parametric method, which does not assume specific production function. DEA compares each producer with only the “best” producer. The production process for each producer is to take a set of inputs and produce a set of outputs. Each producer has a variety of level of inputs and gives a variety of level of outputs. DEA attempts to determine which of the units are most efficient, and to point out specific inefficiencies of the other units. A fundamental assumption behind this method is that if a Decision making unit (DMU₁) is capable to produce $Y(X_1)$ units of output with X_1 inputs, then other DMUs should also be able to do the same if they are operated efficiently. Similarly, if producer DMU₂ is capable of producing $Y(X_2)$ units of output with X_2 inputs, then other DMUs are also capable to produce same production schedule. DEA is a linear programming procedure for a frontier analysis of inputs and outputs. DEA assigns a score of 1 to a unit only when comparisons with other relevant units do not provide evidence of efficiency in the use of any input or output. DEA assigns an efficiency score less than one to (relatively) inefficient units.

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) measures the efficiency of a given decision making units (DMU) in a group relative to the best practicing DMU in that group. It helps to show how relative efficiencies can be estimated and identify units that are relatively less efficient compared to the best performing DMU. The analysis also provides the answers of the following questions:

- i. By how much can input quantities be proportionately reduced without changing the output quantities produced?
- ii. By how much can output quantities be proportionately expanded without altering the input quantities used? (Coelli, 1998)

6. The Application of DEA

There are two versions of the CRS model, input-oriented and output-oriented model. In this study these two are used for measuring production efficiency.

6.1. Application of Input-oriented CRS Model in DEA

The input-oriented model aims to minimize inputs while satisfying the given output levels. The output-oriented model attempts to maximize outputs without requiring more of any of the input variables. The constant returns to scale (CRS) implies that the production technology under consideration is such that, an increase in all the inputs by some proportion results in an increase in the outputs by the same proportion. So, this method identifies the firms that make the most effective use of inputs to produce outputs.

The following equations are used to calculate the relative efficiency for the selected sugar mills for the period under review.

$$\begin{aligned} &\min_{\theta, \lambda} \theta && (1) \\ &s.t \quad -y + y\lambda_2 \geq 0, \\ &\quad \theta x_{it} - X\lambda \geq 0, \\ &\quad \lambda \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

In the empirical analysis, following average data are used:

Table 2: Data Used in DEA

Mills	Production(Mt.)	Sugar cane (Mt.)	Crushing days	Number of Employees	Electricity cost (Tk. In lac)
TSM	6632	100366	82	961	107
NBSM	14936	205927	127	1029	117
KSM	6257	88748	81	768	120
SHSM	3833	55599	63	755	65
C & Co	8983	124641	109	1269	165
FSM	8225	114251	109	890	104

Source: Averages results compiled from annual report of BSFIC for the year 2004-2013.

Here, the researchers have considered input variables as sugarcane used, crushing days, total number of employees, and energy cost for the production process and total production of sugar as output variable in the selected sugar mills under study period.

Table 3: Physical Production: CRS Input Oriented DEA

Mills	te	Output	lambda	Peers	inputs	original	expected	excess	% (excess)
TSM					SCU	100366	91434	8932	9
	0.911	6632	0.444	NBSM	CD	82	56	26	32
				.	TEMP	961	457	504	52
					EC	107	52	55	51
NBSM					SCU	205927	205927	0	0
	1.000	14936	1.000	NBSM	CD	127	127	0	0
					TEMP	1029	1029	0	0
KSM					EC	117	117	0	0
					SCU	88748	86270	2478	3
	0.972	6257	0.419	NBSM	CD	81	53	28	35

					TEMP	768	431	337	44
					EC	120	49	71	59
SHSM					SCU	55599	52483	3116	6
	0.950	3833	0.257	NBSM	CD	63	33	30	48
					TEMP	755	264	491	65
					EC	65	30	35	54
C&Co					SCU	124641	123846	795	1
	0.994	8983	0.601	NBSM	CD	109	76	33	30
					TEMP	1269	619	650	51
					EC	165	71	94	57
FSM					SCU	114251	1196	113055	99
	0.993	8225	0.551	NBSM	CD	109	70	39	36
					TEMP	890	566	324	36
					EC	104	65	39	38

Source: Calculated from the results of the output provided by DEAP Version 2.1.

Table # 3 indicates the utilization position of input variables such as sugarcane used, crushing days, total employee, and energy cost for the production process of sugar as output variable in the selected sugar mills. From the method of CRS input oriented DEA, it was estimated that except NBSM (technical efficiency score is equal to one) all the sugar mills were found inefficient units (technical efficiency score is less than one). If it could be possible to reduce 9 percent of sugarcane, 32 percent of crushing days, 52 percent of the total employees and 51 percent of energy cost by TSM then it would be efficient one like NBSM. Similarly, the unit KSM would be efficient, if it will fulfill target production level 6,257 Mt. of sugar reducing 3 percent of sugarcane, 35 percent of crushing days, 44 percent of total employees and 59 percent of energy cost. However, the rest of the three units had shown inefficiency in the proper use of input variables to fulfill the output target over the period under study. According to technical efficiency scores, the sugar unit NBSM (1.000) stood first position followed by C & Co (0.994), FSM (0.993), KSM (0.972), SHSM (0.952) and TSM (0.911).

6.2. Application of Output-oriented CRS Model in DEA

Output-oriented measures of efficiency determine the extent to which output could be increased by given inputs. The output-oriented measure looks at the extent to which the outputs produced can be increased without an increase in the inputs and hence is known as the output-oriented measure of technical efficiency. Output-oriented CRS in DEA is calculated by the following linear programming formula.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\max_{\theta, \lambda} \theta && (2) \\
 &s.t \quad -y + y\lambda_2 \geq 0, \\
 &\quad \theta x_{it} - X\lambda \geq 0, \\
 &\quad \lambda \geq 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

In the empirical analysis the following average results are used:

Table 4: Physical Production: CRS Output Oriented DEA

Mills	te	lambda	Peers	vars.	Actual	Expected	diff.	% (diff)
TSM	0.911			Prod	6632	7280	648	10
				SCU	100366	100366	0	0
		0.487	NBSM	CD	82	62	20	24
				TEMP	961	501	460	48
				EC	107	57	50	47
NBSM	1.000			Prod	14936	14936	0	0
				SCU	205927	205927	0	0
		1.000	NBSM	CD	127	127	0	0
				TEMP	1029	1029	0	0
				EC	117	117	0	0
KSM	0.972			Prod	6257	6437	180	3
				SCU	88748	88748	0	0
		0.431	NBSM	CD	81	55	26	32
				TEMP	768	443	325	42
				EC	120	51	69	58
SHSM	0.950			Prod	3833	4033	200	5
				SCU	55599	55599	0	0
		0.270	NBSM	CD	63	34	29	46
				TEMP	755	278	477	63
				EC	65	32	33	51
C &Co	0.994			Prod	8983	9040	57	1
				SCU	124641	124641	0	0
		0.605	NBSM	CD	109	77	32	29
				TEMP	1269	623	646	51
				EC	165	71	94	57
FSM	0.993			Prod	8225	8287	62	1
				SCU	114251	114251	0	0
		0.555	NBSM	CD	109	70	39	36
				TEMP	890	571	319	36
				EC	104	65	39	38

Source: Calculated from the results of the output provided by DEAP Version 2.1.

Table # 4 shows the measures of individual input and output variables of the selected sugar mills applying CRS output oriented DEA method. The table shows that NBSM was found to be efficient (benchmark unit with efficiency score one) among selected samples where the output target of sugar production 14,936 Mt. had been fulfilled by using expected input variables. The other five sugar mills TSM, KSM, SHSM, C &Co and FSM are found inefficient where the efficiency scores are found less than one by ranging 0.911 to 0.994. It is found that the output of TSM and KSM could be expanded to 7,280 Mt. and 6,437 Mt. of sugar respectively using same set of expected inputs. On the other hand, using expected set of inputs, SHSM and C & Co could be able to expand outputs level by 5 percent and 1 percent of sugar separately using expected set of inputs. Reducing crushing days, total employees and energy cost by 36 percent, 36 percent

and 38 percent respectively FSM can be able to increase the production level by 1 percent and then the unit would be efficient one like NBSM.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

An input-oriented and output- oriented DEA model with CRS technology is used for estimating overall technical efficiency in small size sugar mills as well as large size sugar mills in Bangladesh. It was estimated that only the sugar unit NBSM (technical efficiency score is equal to one) was found as efficient unit. But rest of the five sugar mills such as; TSM, KSM, SHSM, C &Co and FSM are not able to utilize the inputs crushing days, total employee, and energy cost efficiently. This calls to reduce variables to provide scope for the mills to employ young, motivated and talented workforce. As it is well known that when a firm uses some inputs efficiently may also use all inputs efficiently, so it is to be noted that sugarcane supply must be increased to the inefficient sugar mills as early as possible.

The sugar industry of Bangladesh has reached a critical stage where it has to make a number of crucial decisions. The input variable employees and energy cost are found to be highly underutilized in all the inefficient mills. To increase the operational performance as well as the efficiencies of the sugar mills the following suggestions are recommended:

- i. Managerial skills should be increased;
- ii. Training programs should be arranged by the authority and incentives should be provided to develop skilled manpower;
- iii. Attention should be given to fulfill the targeted output;
- iv. All types of input cost should be minimized;
- v. Uniform sugarcane feeding in mill house should be maintained strictly;
- vi. Production capacity of the sugar mills should be increased;
- vii. Full production capacity of the sugar mills should be utilized; and
- viii. The crushing capacity of the sugar mills should be enhanced.

Acknowledgements

In the study period a number of individuals have helped the researchers in various ways. Foremost, it gives us immense pleasure to express our sincerest gratitude and sense of profound indebtedness to the authority of BSFIC for giving permission to collect data from the mills under study without which this work might not come to the reality. The researchers are grateful to officers and staff of the mills for their cooperation. The researchers also acknowledge the contributions of the researchers and writers with due respect, whose literatures have helped us to complete the study fruitfully.

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